

DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF WORKING ON CONSTRUCTIVE MOLDS

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Annotation: This article will talk about the goals and objectives of language education today, the communicative approach to linguodidactics, in particular, the possibilities of developing linguistic and communicative competencies of students in the process of working on constructive molds.

Key words: Language education, linguistic competence, communicative competence, constructive mold, educational assignment, thinking, perception, skills, communicative literacy, anthropolinguistics, personality-focused education, text, linguistic tool.

It is known that today the social order placed before the education of the native language is aimed at thinking the personality of the reader, understanding the opinion of others and being able to competently state the product of thought in oral and written form, that is, the development of communicative literacy. On this basis, the education of the native language is preceded by the goal of maturing the personality of a socially perfectly formed, able to think independently, with a developed culture of speech and communication, a harmonious student.

The content of native language education based on this purpose:

- to cultivate the thinking activity, mental development, logical thinking of the student;
- directs students to realize the self, material being through the means of expression of the language and to solve the tasks of ensuring that they are able to express their thoughts and feelings within the broad possibilities of the native language. It is necessary that the teacher who carries out these tasks, both scientifically and methodically, always live with the Times hanafas, to be searched tirelessly.

Today's linguistics and methodology have achieved tremendous success. In particular, the anthropocentric approach to language also laid the groundwork for the emergence of unique new perspectives in linguodidactics, concepts such as personality-oriented education, a competency approach to language education.

The term "linguistic competence" was first coined in 1965 by N. Chomsky, "...the ability to understand and create an unlimited number of linguistically correct statements, that is, the ability necessary to carry out certain linguistic activities in the native language, using the studied linguistic means and the rules for their attachment, is defined in the manner". [1]

One of the first in the field of anthropolinguistics was the American scientist D. Hymes (Dell Hymes 1927-09) defined communicative competence as "a body of knowledge about rules that allow us to understand and create texts. [2] It seems that the process of information exchange regarding any situation requires linguistic and communicative competence from a person. The difficulties faced by students in the process of mastering the

sciences, in particular, the inability to fully understand the essence of the information being given, as well as the inability to express their opinion in an understandable way, in many cases testify to the insufficient formation of language competencies in them. Berunius also wrote about this in his time: ...to compose a good speech, it will be necessary to use the collaboration of nahv, aruz, logic Sciences. It is impossible not to care about any of them, a violation of the rule of one of them, not affecting the other two." [3] Indeed, effective communication can come to the surface only when lexical-semantic, grammatical and methodological aspects are taken into account when using language tools used in the process of composing a text, which is recognized as the main point of language education. At this point, it is required to pay attention to one problem that the forms of manifestation of language tools in speech are diverse. This, of course, comes to the surface in connection with the dichotomy of language and speech.

It is known that the morphological word is considered a device, and this device can be expressed through the mold "Ml+Mg". The filling of this mold with concrete morpheme variants in the speech process gives rise to the forms of the word. [4] The question of whether this mold should be filled with concrete morpheme variants and at what level of language this process should be studied is also controversial. Because certain morphemes (word-makers) also cause a change in the grammatical meaning of a word without affecting its lexical meaning, some (form-makers) only serve to express grammatical meaning. In the first case, a new word is made, and in the second case, the form of the word is formed.

In this place, it is correct to study morphemic and word making as a separate section. Because they have their own objects and categories of research. That is, the morphemic(word composition) studies the stem, base and suffixes (both the word yasovchi and the form yasovchi) in the general case. Word making, on the other hand, explores the process of creation of a new lexical meaning. In the process, the word

in addition to making suffixes(morphological method, affixation), other lexical, semantic tools (compositional method, lexical-semantic method) are also studied. It seems to us that it is advisable to study the construction of a form(form) in words not in a separate section, but in the composition of morphology. As long as the grammatical meanings of a word are studied in morphology, the grammatical forms that represent these meanings should also be studied at this stage. Because the morphological word is a molded device "Ml+Mg", as recognized above.

It seems that the word studied in morphology is a morpheme (Ml-lexical morpheme) meaning lexical, as well as a whole(construction, device, mold)arising from the mutual harmonization of a morpheme (Mg-grammatical morpheme) meaning grammatical. Textbooks created in recent years have embodied the interpretation of the constructive (structural) nature of the word. In teaching word composition, the vocabulary and its structural nature in the " Ml+Mg " mold are scientifically –methodically correctly and consistently illuminated in this textbook.

In native language lessons, researching the word as a specific mold-based device will work well, both theoretically and practically. By working on such molds, it is possible to increase the vocabulary of students, the formation of speech skills, while generating knowledge on the constructive nature of the word, as well as language. However, it is important that the exercises and training tasks performed in native language lessons do not become a mechanical process, but, on the contrary, can create a problematic situation for

those who are educated. What the reader needs the text for during reading or listening to the text, what he learns from it conscious interpretation can only occur when one understands what is possible, what should be extracted from the given text, and how it can be used. It can be seen from this that in the issuance of training assignments, two stages arise conditionally: the stage of work with linguistic competencies and the stage of work with communicative competencies. According to the essence of the topic under study, it will also be possible to replace or simultaneously implement their sequence. For example, the teacher recommends a text in the textbook or optional another. Readers, on the other hand, distinguish the same molded ones according to the composition of the words in the text in question. Take the following text as an example:

"In the system of public education, the state language, that is, the native language, has a special place. The native language serves as a means of knowing life, forming moral concepts in students, educating the personal qualities of the younger generation, the heirs of our future. Knowledge and learning of the history, culture, customs, literature and art of the people whose native language is the owner of this language".

Analysis sample:

"Basis" - people, state, mother, separate, moral, young, personal, this, there.

"Base +possessive suffix."- education, role, Future, tool, owner.

"Base +possession q. + agreement " - in the system, language, art, history, culture, tradition, literature.

"Basis + agreement" - language, Life, Generation.

"Base +plural +agreement" - in readers, defines concepts as,

"Base +plural +possessive q. + agreement"- adjectives.

"Base +Action name q."- know, learn.

"Base +ratio" - formation, upbringing.

"Base +possession q. + possession q. + link " - means.

"Base +fluent q."is.

"Base +base" - serves.

It is possible to conduct an educational game "who's who" on the basis of these molds after extracting the belonging of the words in the text to the same mold as above. In this case, students are assigned the task of continuing the line of words in the form. It is also possible to give talented students the task of grouping molds even according to which category the basis belongs to. They group horse-based molds, quality-based molds, verb-based and pronoun-based molds.

In the process of completing the task given above, a linguistic competence about the constructive nature of language is formed in students. And the tasks at the next stage should focus directly on the development of communicative competencies. To achieve this, it is important that the educational task is based on a specific speech situation, that is, it must reflect Real-life communicative situations. When forming a task, there should be no grammar, it should seem to students that they are learning not a new grammatical category, but a new way to express their thoughts. In other words, in order for him to understand the constructive nature of the word, a given assignment must create a situation in which the educator must use this linguistic skill in his speech. In addition, it is important that this situation is relevant for the speech practice of students. For example, readers are instructed to approach someone within a given topic with a request, story, suggestion, assessment,

comment, and other purposes. The process requires, however, that the words used should be intact, not piecemeal. Naturally, they will not be able to do this. The teacher asks them what are the causes of the problem that has arisen forming this process in a way of controversy further increases the effectiveness of the lesson. On this basis, they realize the structural nature of the word in the "Ml+Mg" mold and acquire a skill about the need of each part in the formation of their speech. As a result, the harmonization of the formation of linguistic and communicative skills is achieved.

In personality-focused education, the most significant activities are those that create the conditions for the emergence of the student's own speech. Without such exercises, it is impossible to develop communicative competence. These exercises are problematic, include discussion, Play, Project. In the process of completing such tasks :

- the vocabulary of students increases;
- practice logical actions such as analogy, comparison, classification, generalization and inference;
- as a result, knowledge of the structural nature of the language is strengthened;
- in addition to the development of linguistic competence, the ground is laid for the development of communicative competence;
- allows you to harmonize communicative and linguistic competencies.

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